

Future Converged Fixed/Mobile Access Networks in the 6G Era (Invited)

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Abstract *Enhanced connectivity, performance, efficiency, and flexibility on both 6G and future optical access networks are key factors that will be allowed by AI, Edge Computing, HS-PON/PtP, vHS-PON/PtP, All-Photonic-Networks, extended CTI, Open-RAN and many more features. ©2024 The Authors*

Introduction

The 6th generation (6G) of mobile networks will be developed for sustainability, aiming to connect the unconnected and will offer ubiquitous intelligence, security, and resilience. Six usage scenarios have been identified as an extension from 5G: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) will transition towards immersive communication, Massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC) will evolve into Massive Communication, and Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) will transform into Hyper-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (HURLLC). Ubiquitous Connectivity, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Communication, and Integrated Sensing and Communication represent three new areas of potential usage for 6G [1].

Figure 1 was created by the International Telecommunication Union Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) for International Mobile Telecommunications-2030 (IMT-2030), illustrating the palette diagram of 6G capabilities. Estimated figure targets are also represented for research and exploration within the framework of IMT-2030.

Mobile and fixed network operators consider that 6G must facilitate a smooth migration from 5G and coexist with previous mobile generations. It will depend on technology support and enablers

to enhance capacity per cell. The Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) configuration will be improved with higher order MIMO and narrower beamforming, which will facilitate multi-user configuration within a cell.

The exploitation of frequency bands FR1 (0.41 to 7.125 GHz) and FR2 (24.25 to 71 GHz) has played a crucial role in the evolution process of 5G networks. As the era of 5G-Advanced and 6G approaches, a third frequency range has been under discussion within international regulatory and industrial consortia, particularly in last ITU meeting. FR3, also known as the upper mid-band, ranges from 7.125 to 24.25 GHz. This frequency band offers new prospects for mobile communication technologies. With better MIMO and extended frequency ranges, 6G will be able to extend its data-rate capacity by a factor of 10.

To increase the radio quality and adapt it, and to collect sensitive data around the mobile networks, sensing tools will be developed over 6G radio networks [2]. Sub-THz bands are specifically of interest for developing sensing, with its wide possible coverage range that goes through walls for example. 6G could also include satellite communication as part of the Radio Access Network (RAN) with specific interconnections to ensure real-time seamless communication and connect the unconnected. Public radio access points in various locations such as transport nodes or shopping malls could offer high-speed connectivity and potentially support mm-Wave small cells' backhaul needs. Yet, ensuring compatibility with cellular services and addressing security concerns remain critical challenges there.

6G will benefit from core (entirely) and RAN (partially) network functions virtualization, an evolution with more and more network softwarization, following current trends of Open-RAN initiatives, as depicted in Figure 2.

As much as possible, any hardware or software 6G feature should be managed within a cloud instance. 6G will be the mobile network of 2030s that will enable more and more AI and intelligence in the network and services.

Fig. 1: "Palette diagram" of 6G capabilities, source ITU-R

Nonetheless, enhancing energy efficiency has consistently been a primary objective in the design of both network infrastructure and user devices. Alongside improving energy efficiency, it is imperative to minimize the total energy consumption and limit Green House Gaz emissions as well as support circular economy for sustainable progress. This necessitates the development of power-efficient and zero-emission 6G technology solutions for both backhaul and local access, facilitating the utilization of small-scale renewable energy sources.

Optical Access for future mobile Networks

Regarding 6G mobile X-haul connectivity, fibre is

Fig. 2: Evolution from tradition RAN to Open RAN

expected to be the privileged option, with baud rates projected to reach more than a Terabit for some configurations of antenna sites.

While 50 Gigabit Passive Optical Networks (50G-PON) are reaching finalization by ITU-T as a future generation of PON deployed in FTTH networks. Challenges such as cost, power consumption, and complexity persist for higher bitrates [3]. Discussions on a 200G-PON technology within Very High Speed PON (vHSP) scope suggest support for network evolution beyond 2030. Such high bitrate TDM-PONs (Time Division Multiplexing-PONs) could be suitable for mobile backhaul with fibre sharing but they face limitations due to packet delay variation and strict congestion traffic policy for mobile fronthaul. Specific “private” networks, like campus & industry & distributed antenna system, could offer an opportunity for PON to serve x-haul 6G.

Point to Point (PtP) links are evolving towards bidirectional transmission up to 100 Gbit/s over 10, 20 or 40km of fibre reach [4], and discussions on 200 Gbit/s and 400 Gbit/s are underway [5]. With such capacity, PtP links are anticipated to remain the preferred choice for extensive local connectivity to mobile networks, while WDM-PON or TDM-PONs could be alternatives in areas with either limited fibre availability or extended reach fiber network. WDM solutions for mobile networks are emerging at 25 Gbit/s [6], with standard specifications expected from ITU-T [7]. For higher bitrates, 50 Gbit/s or 100 Gbit/s, discussions on the definition of new DWDM spectral grids in the O-band are expected to mitigate chromatic dispersion effects in the C-band. Otherwise, digital signal processing or more complex

optics could be required.

The 5th generation of fixed networks (F5G) is progressing towards F5G advanced specifications to provide over 10 times higher bandwidth, denser fibre connections, better reliability, better energy efficiency as well as sensing with 1m accuracy, <1 ms end-to-end latency, autonomous level 4 [8]. F5G Advanced offers a range of key features including higher network speeds enabled by technologies like >10G-Fibre To The Room and 50G-PON, as well as the integration of cloud computing into optical networks for on-demand services. It also focuses on the definition of functions, architectures, and interfaces for autonomous networking, enhancing Quality of Experience (QoE) through automation, and developing energy-efficient architectures. Additionally, it highlights the advantages of optical communication in industrial sectors and emphasizes the need for collaboration between networking and computing to optimize service quality and enable low-delay services. With all these features, F5G advanced technologies will have enablers to support future mobile networks including 5G and 6G. Going a bit further, we presented in [9] some projections towards the sixth generation of fixed networks (F6G) for beyond 2030.

IOWN Global Forum proposes to enhance mobile networks of 2030 by transitioning to all-optical connections with All-Photonic Networks (APN), expanding endpoints from site-to-site to memory-to-memory integration. Some metrics have been proposed in [10], showing increased bandwidth per endpoint to over 10 Tbit/s, minimized latency, automated system failure handling, and reduced jitter for improved performance.

More specifically to reduce the latency, the current Cooperative Transport Interface (CTI) specifications are inadequate for short Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs) and Mid-Haul/Back-Haul (MH/BH) in upcoming mobile networks. To address this, there's a need to enhance CTI specifications. IOWN proposes to reach end-to-end low-latency as the APN controller can directly receive mobile information from the CU/DU through an “extended CTI” [11]. Moreover, optical switching schemes for dynamic load balancing and power consumption reduction have been proposed associating APN with RAN Intelligent controllers.

Towards flexible and autonomous networks for fixed-mobile convergence

Future fixed networks will need to increase their resilience by incorporating greater redundancy to minimize network downtime. Advanced network monitoring capabilities, as well as technologies

such as fiber sensing and AI/Machine Learning, are expected to facilitate the transition towards autonomous networks. The interaction between AI and 6G can be seen in two ways: AI enhancing communication and communication empowering AI. These dual dynamics will open new opportunities for the advancement of 6G networks.

In the meantime, distributed RAN, virtualized RAN and centralization induce major evolutions in the RAN architecture, both on the hardware and software parts [12]. Open RAN (O-RAN) and Cloud RAN can also leverage energy efficiency improvements with RAN architecture evolution. That will certainly impact fixed network evolutions as well. Evolution to O-RAN is a key enabler for RAN sharing and network slicing which rely on partitioning the network infrastructure into virtualized segments to cater to diverse service requirements, such as bandwidth, latency, and security, within a single physical network that is fully interoperable. This enables efficient resource utilization for any operator and customization of services for various applications, including residential, business, and mobile connectivity, while maintaining isolation and performance guarantees for each slice.

Moreover, the transition from traditional OLT management to Software Defined Network-based controllers involves separating management functions from hardware and implementing them in software controllers, with possible convergence with the Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC). This shift enhances flexibility and scalability by providing centralized and coordinated control and programmability and will lead to more dynamic, efficient, and converged OLT and RAN management.

With more and more network function virtualization, automation and flexibility expected in future networks, fixed and mobile network convergence will not anymore take place only where physical interconnections exist (today in the central office and at antenna sites). But this might not be the best option in terms of carbon footprint,

network sharing to generalize computing and server functions such as Mobile Edge Computing and edge AI so close to the user. Optical networks architecture must then mature to support these evolutions towards autonomous networks with flexibility expected from the physical layer to the protocol layer to ease transparent end-to-end connectivity.

Enhanced photonic switching with multi-Tbit/s capacities for next generation central offices are being developed in the OCTAPUS project with dedicated SDN controller to support TSN for future mobile networks. An optical bypass of the OLT with PtP demonstrating flexible architectures for low latency and power savings capabilities has been demonstrated in [13].

Recently, new designs of Hollow Core Fibres demonstrated attenuation profiles with losses as low as 0.11 dB/km [14]. These innovative fibres could potentially contribute to reduce latency to 3.5 μ s per km of fiber (instead of 5 μ s/km with SSMF) in transport networks for mobile. However, improvements in the production process (longer spools, fiber coupling, soldering processes, spectral band extension) are still necessary to demonstrate significant interest for deployment of new fibres.

Conclusions

Future convergence in fixed and mobile access networks within the 6G era will be present in many ways in the future decade. This convergence promises enhanced synergy and seamless integration between diverse network infrastructures, enabling enhanced connectivity, performance, efficiency and flexibility. By leveraging advanced technologies such as end-to-end network slicing, edge computing, and AI-driven optimization, 6G networks will generate necessary evolution of the optical transport with converged control, monitoring and orchestration required. However, challenges related to standardization, interoperability, and security must be addressed to fully realize the potential of this convergence.

Fig. 3: Schematic view of what could be future access networks for 6G

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